

Utilizing Mechanoluminescent Materials for Improving the Mode I Fracture Test

Nassos Spetsieris

Michael Gower

Agenda

- Introduction
 - The Mode I Fracture Test
 - Mechanoluminescence
- Specimen Preparation
- Test Setup
- Test Results
- Conclusions and Next Steps

Introduction | The Mode I Fracture Test

- Fracture is a complex and often unexpected phenomenon in materials
- Broken down in 3 modes in order to simplify and predict
- Mode I is the case where load is applied normal to the crack's propagation
- In the case of laminates → Interlaminar fracture toughness G_{IC}

Introduction | The Mode I Fracture Test

- Measuring the crack's position **accurately** during the test run is essential.
- Traditionally, the monitoring is manual with the use of a travelling microscope
- **Highly** affected by operator error and uncertainties

Mechanoluminescence

Fractoluminescence

Breaking of material's atomic and chemical bonds

Plasma discharge

Triboluminescence

Contact or separation between specific materials

Triboelectric (static) discharge

Deformation Luminescence

Elastico-luminescence

Plastico-luminescence

Light emission from the recombination of **released trapped electrons** from lattice in the luminescent centres

Specimen Preparation

- Two main ML compounds available:

SAOED Phosphors
($\text{SrAl}_2\text{O}_4:\text{Eu}^{2+},\text{Dy}^{3+}$)

Zinc Sulfides
($\text{ZnS}:\text{Mn}$)

The SAOED pigment (*left*) has a distinctive yellow colour, while the zinc sulfide pigment (*right*) is light orange.

Average particle sizes:

SAOED \rightarrow $20\mu\text{m}$

ZnS:Mn \rightarrow $3\mu\text{m}$

Specimen Preparation

- Pigments procured in different grades (3 - 45 μ m) & as off-the-shelf premixed paints.
- In total, **10** systems were prepared from **7** different compounds:
 - One of the systems (S1) was provided after professional preparation & coating.
 - One system (S3) consists of zinc sulfide pigment, the rest are SAOED.
 - Six systems (S5-S10) were premixed off-the-self, the rest were mixed with epoxy resin to 7:3 w/w.
 - The coating for five systems (S2-S6) was applied with a brush, the rest using compressed air.

Specimen Preparation

- For systems S2-S10, the specimen is a 3mm thick CFRP UD laminate in a load-block double-cantilever beam (DCB) configuration, according to **BS ISO 22838**.
- For the outsourced system, a bi-material (aluminium and woven CFRP) DCB specimen was coated with S1. This specimen configuration follows **BS ISO 25217**.

DCB specimen according to BS ISO 22838

DCB specimen according to BS ISO 25217

Specimen Preparation | Summary

System #	ML Compound	Mixing	Coating
S1	SAOED	Epoxy Resin	Spray
S2	SAOED	Epoxy Resin	Brush
S3	ZnS:MN	Epoxy Resin	Brush
S4	SAOED	Epoxy Resin	Brush
S5	SAOED	Premixed	Brush
S6	SAOED	Premixed	Spray
S7	SAOED	Premixed	Airbrush
S8	SAOED	Premixed	Airbrush
S9	SAOED	Premixed	Airbrush
S10	SAOED	Premixed	Airbrush

Test Setup

A video extensometry system allows for monitoring the crack propagation and ML activity during the test.

By remotely accessing this computer as well as the test machine control unit, we can safely test under consistent dark-room conditions.

Test Setup

Excitation under UV light (~365nm) is required to activate the ML of the material.

After excitation, there are two properties that comprise the ML response

1. Afterglow (Noise)
2. Mechanoluminescence (Signal)

Upon excitation, $N > S$ but gradually afterglow decays to allow for more intense ML.

Therefore an “ageing” phase of 1-5 minutes is required to get detectable light emission during the test.

Test Results

- The trade-off between afterglow and ML (or afterglow decay) is visible in the beginning.
- The exact point of the crack initiation can be identified.
- By comparing the two sides, one can quantify the crack front position mismatch throughout the test.
- Although faint, the light emission appears to be fluctuating, indicating the constant transition between accumulating and releasing strain energy to allow for the crack front to propagate.

Test Results

- For systems S2-S10 a strong ML signal could not be obtained.
- Inconsistencies observed:
 - Absence of afterglow
 - ML signal fading out mid-test
 - Absence of afterglow and ML altogether
 - Sustained afterglow throughout the test

Potential causes:

- Uneven coating application
- Poor mixing ratio
- Weakened ML material in off-the-shelf paints
- Thickness of UD DCB specimens

- The need to atomise the epoxy resin ML (S2-S4) mixes to use with an airbrush poses serious H&S complications and makes the adoption of this method more challenging.
- Another hindrance lies in the visual assessment of the uniformity of the ML coating during application. Ideally a UV-light equipped fume cupboard would be required.
- An FEA model was developed for the purpose of validating the ML signal intensity around the crack tip.

- The utilisation of mechanoluminescent materials as stress sensors for the purpose of monitoring crack growth showed good potential.
- There are several issues that need addressing in order to streamline this process and achieve repeatable measurements.
- Employing image processing techniques to track the ML signal throughout the footage could allow for automated crack front detection, minimising measurement uncertainty.

Conclusions | Next steps

- Ensure reputable way of applying thin uniform coatings.
- Trial different mixing ratios and binder materials.
- Modify specimen geometry for stiffer arms and more direct load introduction.
- Explore intermittent UV excitation with shorter afterglow decay times.
- Validate ML signal intensity around crack tip against FEA model.
- Placement of top-view camera to monitor crack front real-time propagation

Thank you for your attention.

Questions?

Nassos Spetsieris
nassos.spetsieris@npl.co.uk

Michael Gower
michael.gower@npl.co.uk

